

Pagans under the Emperor Julian

By Jeremy Swist, Brandeis University

Entry tags: Roman Religions, Asia Minor, Greek Cult, Indo-European Religion, Mystery Religion, Ancient Syrian Religion, Ancient Mediterranean, Mysticism, Rome, Religious Practice, Gaul, Divination, Roman State Religion, Polytheistic, Phrygia, Mithraism, Hellenistic Religions, Anatolian Religions, Lydian Religions, Pergamon Religions, Phrygian Religions, [Religions of] Pontus Kingdom, Egyptian Religions, Greek Religions, Greek Polis Religions, Greek Domestic Religions, Greek Mystery Cults, Greek Philosophical Traditions, Roman Religious Traditions, Italic Religions, Syncretic Religions, Religious Group

Practitioners of traditional, indigenous, and non-Abrahamic religions and mystery cults under the Roman Empire, even during the brief reign of Julian (r. 361-363), were hardly a unified group, except in the mind of the emperor himself and his circle of intellectual elites. Although the term "pagan" originated as a Christian pejorative for non-Christian gentiles, it is more adequate than either "polytheist," which excludes non-Abrahamic monotheists, or "traditionalist," which erases groups that are relatively more recent than the familial and state cults of, for instance, Athens or Rome, i.e. Mithraists and Manichaeans. Individuals' participation in religious practices, moreover, is not always consistent with inner convictions that are usually impossible to discern. Julian's religious beliefs and policies, nevertheless, attempted to integrate the rich diversity of Roman pagans into a single, artificial category in contradistinction to Christianity, which he regarded as an anti-religion, tantamount to atheism, that worshiped corpses rather than gods. Julian saw legitimate religions, Judaism included, as necessarily tied to ethnicity and geography. The "ethnic god" of each polis or ethnos accounted for their essential characteristics, e.g. the Romans were descended from Mars and so were warlike, while the Athenians inherited their philosophical tendencies from Athena. Julian called the Christians by the demonym "Galileans" in order to deny the religion's universality and restrict it to the ethnos of Jesus. As pontifex maximus and Hellenic Neoplatonist, the emperor not only treated Roman culture and religion as "from beginning to end, Greek;" he also placed all cults throughout the empire under his purview in a syncretic and henotheistic manner: every ethnic god was an emanation of the supreme god, which the emperor identified with the sun-god Helios. Basing his theology on the Neoplatonism of the Syrian Iamblichus of Chalcis, Julian's Helios manifested itself in a triune hierarchy: at the top was Helios the King of All (pambasileus), which is "beyond being," source of all being, and equal to the Plato's Form of the Good and the One of Plotinus; King Helios (basileus) occupies the middle rank, the father of the gods and creator of the cosmos identified with Zeus and Plato's Demiurge; lowest is the visible Sun, the conduit of Helios' blessings upon the sensible cosmos. Julian and his inner circle also drew from Iamblichus the conviction that contact and spiritual union with Helios and the other gods cannot be achieved through intellectual contemplation (theoria) alone; divine blessings must be secured suprarationally through ritual practices such as prayer and blood sacrifice, while mystical ascent can be achieved only through the "hieratic art" of theurgy, in which the celebrant made suitable through purification participates in the "god-work" (theourgia) that sustains and renews the cosmos. In Julian's quasi-ecclesiastical vision of ecumenical paganism, theurgists functioned as high priests over provincial congregations of local cults, and organized philanthropic relief of the poor and sick in competition with Christian charity. Although generally supportive of the emperor's program of temple reconstruction, religious toleration, and redirection of imperial subsidies back to traditional cults, very few of the empire's pagans shared their emperor's radical vision. While the Iamblichean school of theurgic Neoplatonism persisted into the sixth century among pagan elites such as Proclus and Damascius at the Athenian Academy, in Julian's day it was represented by a minority of philosophers. Even the majority of Neoplatonists were heirs more to Plotinus and Porphyry, who valued rational contemplation above ritual practice, and especially rejected blood offerings. Likewise, animal sacrifice had already been falling out of fashion by the fourth century, such that toothless prohibitions by Christian emperors such as Constantius II caused little trouble and did not extend to offerings of incense or cakes. On a political level, Julian's

ideological polarization of Christianity versus a united front of paganism rarely corresponded to reality. While the Altar of Victory that Constantius had removed from the Curia was restored under Julian, the largely traditionalist Roman Senate had not supported Julian's revolt against Constantius, while the army's initial choice of Julian's coreligionist Salutius to succeed the dead emperor in 363, which Salutius refused such that the Christian Jovian was elevated instead, suggests that an emperor's personal religious affiliation was not so high a priority. It is telling of general attitudes at the time that the pagan soldier turned historian who served in that fateful Persian campaign, Ammianus Marcellinus, praised Julian highly for his military and political virtues, but largely criticized his zealous religious policies, such as his extravagant slaughter of sacrificial animals and edict forbidding Christians from serving as public school teachers. Although Julian did not violently persecute Christians, he nevertheless resembled the likes of Decius and Diocletian in that his divisive rhetoric of militant paganism largely clashed with the tolerant attitudes of the vast majority of the empire's citizens, to a similar degree as the fulminations of Christian bishops such as Ambrose and John Chrysostom did not reflect the feelings of most Christians toward their pagan compatriots. The lynching of one such bishop in Alexandria, George of Cappadocia, by a pagan mob inspired by Julian's accession in 361, should therefore not testify to pagans' general attitudes towards Christians during his reign. In sum, the brevity of Julian's 18-month career as sole Augustus precluded any potential success, and thus had little effect on the continuity or discontinuity of traditional practices in communities and households, which were largely maintained as a matter of civic pride and duty to ancestors. The pace of conversion to Christianity accelerated as much for its social and political opportunities as the religion of the new establishment as for its promises of spiritual reward on earth and in heaven.

Date Range: 361 CE - 363 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe

Most of Western Europe and the Mediterranean, but tagged only as "Western Europe".

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Wright, W. C. (ed. & trans.) 1913-1923. *The Works of the Emperor Julian*. Vols. 1-3. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Source 2: Hamilton, W. (ed. & trans.) 1986. *Ammianus Marcellinus: The Later Roman Empire (A.D. 354-378)*. London: Penguin Books.
- Source 3: Norman, A. F. (ed. & trans.) 1969. *Libanius: The Julianic Orations*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Author:Flavius_Claudius_Julianus
Notes: The Works of the Emperor Julian, translated into English by W. C. Wright (Wikisource)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.loebclassics.com/browse?t1=author:julian>

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

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– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

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↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

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↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

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↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

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– At home

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Pagans under the late Roman Empire held a diversity of belief about the soul/spirit and its relationship to the body, its mortality or immortality, and its materiality or immateriality.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans’ behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Adultery:
 - No

 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Pagans under the late Roman Empire were comprised of polytheists, monotheists, henotheists, and atheists. The majority were polytheists while monotheism, henotheism, and atheism was more characteristic of elites and intellectuals.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Pagan gods were generally represented anthropomorphically in art and iconography, though their divine forms were not usually confined within human forms. Elites and intellectuals at this time sometimes doubted that these gods ever took human form on earth, but rather manifested through lesser intermediaries such as demons.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of Roman pagans at this time believed in a celestial supreme deity, either a weather god like Zeus and Jupiter, or a solar god like Helios or Mithras. Julian and other Neoplatonists incorporated and subsumed these and other deities within a single, henotheistic godhead.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: Julian claimed a special relationship with Helios and considered himself an emanation therefrom, and some of his contemporaries subscribed to this in their conceptions of the imperial cult.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– No

Notes: Elites and intellectuals, especially those influenced by philosophy, often idealized the gods and considered them morally perfect beings, and read the myths of ancient poets concerning these gods allegorically in order to account for the all-too-human imperfections of gods such as Zeus.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Yes

Notes: While pagan conceptions of their deities varied, most imbued in them some form of omniscience, including knowledge of the future.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs in the emotional status of pagan deities varied. Intellectuals, influenced by philosophy, tended to conceive of the gods as wholly rational beings unaffected by human emotions or passions.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs in the emotional status of pagan deities varied. Intellectuals, influenced by philosophy, tended to conceive of the gods as wholly rational beings unaffected by human emotions or passions.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs in the necessity and function of animal sacrifice were highly variable, though by Julian's day this practice was falling out of favor in preference to offerings of cakes, incense, and other non-blood offerings.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Pagan beliefs in divine communication highly varied, but many included dreams, signs in the heavens and the organs of sacrificial animals, fortune telling, and oracles. However, many divinatory and oracular practices were falling out of fashion at this time, including through legal prohibitions delivered by Christian emperors. Julian attempted to reinvigorate many of these practices, some of which he practiced himself.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Pagans under the late Roman Empire held a diversity of belief about the afterlife, including skepticism and disbelief in its existence.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Pagans under the late Roman Empire held a diversity of belief about reincarnation and the transmigration of the soul. This belief was most commonly held among certain groups of Pythagoreans and Platonists.

↳ In a human form:
– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:
– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
– Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– I don't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Pagans under the late Roman Empire held a diversity of belief about the soul/spirit and its relationship to the body, its mortality or immortality, and its materiality or immateriality.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

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↳ A supreme high god is present:

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– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: While pagan conceptions of their deities varied, most imbued in them some form of omniscience, including knowledge of the future.

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↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs in the necessity and function of animal sacrifice were highly variable, though by Julian's day this practice was falling out of favor in preference to offerings of cakes, incense, and other non-blood offerings.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Pagan beliefs in divine communication highly varied, but many included dreams, signs in the heavens and the organs of sacrificial animals, fortune telling, and oracles. However, many divinatory and oracular practices were falling out of fashion at this time, including through legal prohibitions delivered by Christian emperors. Julian attempted to reinvigorate many of these practices, some of which he practiced himself.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– No

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

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Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

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Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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